

Supplementary Material 4 - Table S3

Frequency of mental health outcome measures for type of extreme weather event

EWE	# of papers	Rural/urban (frequency)	Countries (frequency)	Mental Health Outcome Measures (frequency)
Cyclone	3	Rural (2)	Bangladesh (2), India	Anxiety (2) Depression (3) Psychological distress Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) Suicidal ideation
Drought	12	Rural (8), Both (2)	Australia (4), Bangladesh, Botswana (2), Ethiopia, India (3), USA	Anxiety Community drought-related stress Depression (3) Distress Occupational psychosocial stress ("job strain") Personal drought-related stress Posttraumatic growth Psychological distress (2) Self-harm Suicide deaths (2) Suicide attempts Suicide ideation (2) Thoughts of self-harm Trauma symptoms (2)
Flood	41	Rural (11) Urban (14) Both (4) Semi-urban (1) Suburban/ semi-rural (1)	Australia (2), Bangladesh (2), Burundi, Canada, China (7), Ghana, India (9), Malaysia (1), Indonesia (5), Pakistan, Spain, Thailand, UK (7), USA (2)	Anger Anxiety (17) Children's PTSD symptoms Chronic PTSD Chronic stress Depression (22) Depression, anxiety and stress Drugs used in management of common mental disorders Dysfunctional cognitions (2) Emotional functioning – children General psychiatric morbidity Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) (3) Health related quality of life Impact of event Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) Mania (2) Mental health service utilization Obsessive compulsive disorder Panic disorder Parent PTSD symptoms Parent reported PTSD symptoms for children Post Traumatic Stress Reactivity (3) Posttraumatic cognition Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (29) Posttraumatic Stress Symptoms (PTSS) (2) Probable anxiety Probable depression Probable PTSD Problems with memory Psychological distress Psychosis (2) Risk of suicide Rumination Schizophrenia admissions Service use for all other mental health/behavioral disorders Service use for anxiety disorders Service use for bipolar disorders Service use for depressive disorders Service use for schizophrenic and psychotic disorders Service use for substance and addictive disorders Service use for trauma and stress disorders Sleep disorders Somatic symptoms

EWE	# of papers	Rural/urban (frequency)	Countries (frequency)	Mental Health Outcome Measures (frequency)
				Still distressed (2) Stress (3) Substance abuse (2) Substance abuse – Alcohol Suicidal attempts Suicidal ideation (5) Suicidal tendency Suicide deaths Symptoms of anxiety Symptoms of depression Symptoms of dissociation Well-being
Extreme Cold/ cold spells	6	Urban (6)	China (4), Sweden, USA	Affective disorder outpatient visits (minus depression) Anxiety outpatient visits Depressive disorder outpatient visits Mental disorder - admissions Mental disorder outpatient visits Mental health ED visits (2) Mood disorder ED visits Neurotic disorder ED visits Psychiatric emergency visits Psychoactive substance use ED visits Schizophrenia admissions Schizophrenia ED visits Schizophrenia outpatient visits
Extreme heat / heat waves	32	Rural (1), Urban (18), Both (6)	Australia (3), Belgium, Brazil, Canada, China (7), Finland, India (2), Japan (3), Philippines, South Africa, South Korea (2), Spain (2), Sweden, Switzerland, Taiwan, UK USA (8), Vietnam (3)	Mental and behavioural disorders – admissions (3) Adult personality and behavior disorder ED visits Affective disorder outpatient visits (minus depression) Alzheimer's deaths within 2 months of hospitalization Alzheimer's disease urgent hospital admissions Alzheimer's hospitalizations Anxiety disorder ED visits Anxiety emergency admissions Anxiety outpatient visits Anxiety, stress-related and somatoform disorder ED visits Behavior and mood disorders usually associated with childhood and youth - admissions Complex behavioural disorders - admissions Complex behavioural disorders associated with physiological disorders and somatic factors admissions Crisis help seeking Dementia ED visits Dementia emergency admissions Depression emergency admissions Depressive disorder outpatient visits Depressive symptoms Developmental disorders - admissions (3) Mental and behavioral disorder related deaths Mental and behavioral disorders - admissions Mental and behavioral disorders caused by use of psychoactive substances - admissions (2) Mental and behavioural disorder - ED visits Mental disorder ED visits Mental disorder outpatient visits Mental disorders admissions (8) Mental health admissions (2) Mental health ED visits (6) Mental health emergency admissions Mental retardation admissions (2) Mood (affective) disorders Mood disorder ED visits (3) Mood disorders - admissions (3) Neurotic disorder ED visits Neurotic disorder hospitalizations Neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorder admissions (3) Psychiatric emergency visits Psychoactive substance use ED visits (2) Psychoactive substance use hospitalizations

EWE	# of papers	Rural/urban (frequency)	Countries (frequency)	Mental Health Outcome Measures (frequency)
				Schizophrenia - admissions (2) Schizophrenia ED visits (2) Schizophrenia emergency admissions Schizophrenia outpatient visits Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorder ED visits Self-harm ambulance cases Self-harm ED visits Substance use ED visits Suicide deaths (6) Suicide watch incidents Suicide-related ambulance calls Suicides per 100,000
Extreme rainfall	2	Urban (1), Both (1)	China (2)	Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) Resilience Rumination Schizophrenia admissions
Hurricane	21	Urban (10), Both (2), Suburban/ semi-rural (1)	Bahamas, Puerto Rico, USA (19)	Acute psychological distress Adjustment disorder ED visits and hospitalizations Adolescent psychological distress Alcohol and substance use ED visits and hospitalizations Alcohol use Anxiety (3) Anxiety related ED visits and hospitalization Binge drinking in past year Cannabis use Cigarette use Days a month of poor physical or mental health Depression (5) Depressive symptoms Functional impairment Generalized worries Global distress High Stress Hurricane-related distress Major depressive disorder (MDD) (2) Mental health related ED visit and hospitalizations Mood disorder ED visits and hospitalisations Opioid abuse Perceived stress Poor mental health days Posttraumatic stress Posttraumatic Stress Symptoms (PTSS) (2) Psychological distress Psychosis ED visits and hospitalizations Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (8) Posttraumatic Stress Symptoms (PTSS) (2) Recreational drug use Sadness Self-reported mental health difficulties in past 30 days Substance abuse - alcohol (2) Suicidal ideation (2) Suicide and intentional harm ED visits and hospitalizations
Snowstorm	2	Urban (1), Both (1)	UK, USA	Emotional upheaval Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)
Tornado	6*	Urban (5), Both (1)	China (5), USA	Burnout (2) Depression (2) Mindfulness (3) Parental Attachment Posttraumatic Growth (PTG) Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (4) Posttraumatic Stress Symptoms (PTSS) PTSD Reaction Index Regulatory emotional self-efficacy
Typhoon	9	Urban (4), Both (4)	Philippines (8), Taiwan	Acute stress disorder (2) Centrality of event and mental health outcomes Depression

EWE	# of papers	Rural/urban (frequency)	Countries (frequency)	Mental Health Outcome Measures (frequency)
				Depression, anxiety, and stress (2) Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) Insomnia Monthly visits for adjustment reactions Monthly visits for all stress-associated illness Monthly visits for anxiety Monthly visits for depressive disorders Monthly visits for episodic mood disorders Monthly visits for PTSD Monthly visits for stress-associated insomnia Positive metacognitions and positive meta-emotions Posttraumatic cognitions (2) Posttraumatic Growth (PTG) Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (5) Psychological distress (2) Sensory-based memory quality of traumatic event
Wildfire	28	Rural (6), Urban (13), Both (3)	Australia (11), Canada (12), Greece, USA (4)	Agoraphobia Alcohol use Alcohol use disorder Anger Anxiety (6) Avoidant attachment style Coping strategies Depression (10) Drug use disorder Drug-related problems Fear of death Fire-related PTSD Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) (5) Grief Insomnia (3) Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) (6) Major depressive episodes (2) Mental and emotional well-being Mental health service utilisation Nicotine dependence Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder Panic disorder Perceived stress Perinatal PTSD Peritraumatic dissociative experiences Peritraumatic distress Physical activity and well-being Posttraumatic Growth (PTG) Posttraumatic stress Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (17) Posttraumatic Stress Symptoms (PTSS) Psychological distress (4) Psychopathology symptoms Psychotropic medication prescription rates - antidepressants Psychotropic medication prescription rates - antipsychotics Psychotropic medication prescription rates - anxiolytics Psychotropic medication prescription rates - hypnotics Psychotropic medication prescription rates - mood stabilizers Severe mental illness Social phobia Somatic symptoms Stress (2) Substance abuse - Alcohol (5) Substance abuse - Drugs Substance abuse (3) Suicidal ideation (2) Tobacco use Well-being

ED: Emergency Department; PTSD: Posttraumatic Stress Disorder

*5 of the 6 studies used the same baseline population data